

EFFECT OF MECHANICAL ANTIDOTE ON TOXICITY OF SEED EXTRACT OF *THEVETIA PERUVIANA* IN ALBINO RAT-FORENSIC CONSIDERATION

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ABSTRACT

The present study has been carried out with an objective to find out the mechanical antidote for *Thevetia peruviana* seed poison which was commonly used as suicidal poison. Albino rat was used as animal model and following biochemical parameters such as AST, ALT, Bilirubin, Creatinine, Urea and protein have been examined from blood. After examination it was found that antidote number 4 was showing better result in comparison to antidote number 3. Finally it was concluded that antidote number 4 can be effectively used for *Thevetia peruviana* poisoning to render the onset of toxic effect.

Key Words: Mechanical Antidote, Biochemical Parameters, *Thevetia Peruviana* Seeds and Forensic Importance

INTRODUCTION

Thevetia peruviana is an ever – green ornamental dicotyledonous shrub that belongs to Apocyanaceae family, also known as Kaner, Kuner, Pila-kanir, Zard-kunel with identifying features like funnel shaped, spirally twisted yellow flowers, globular green fruits. It is found in the tropics and sub – tropics regions of India. It grows about 10 – 18 feet high; the leaves are spirally arranged, linear and about 13-15 cm in length. There are two varieties of the plant (Behcet *et al.*, 2010) one with yellow flowers, yellow oleander, and the other with purple flowers, Nerium oleander. Both varieties produce flower and fruit all over year providing a steady supply of seeds. Grown as hedges, they can produce between 400 – 800 fruits per annum depending on the rainfall pattern and plant age. The flowers are funnel-like with petals that are spirally twisted. The fruits are somewhat globular, with fleshy mesocarp and have a diameter of 4-5 cm. The fruits are usually green in colour and become black on ripening. Each fruit contains a nut which is longitudinally and transversely divided. The fruit contains one to four seeds in its kernel. The plants bear milky juice in all organs. All parts of the plant are toxic, due to the presence of glycosides. The seed contains 60 – 65% oil and the cake comprise of 30-37% protein. Despite the fact that there is high level of oil and protein in the seed, it remains non – edible because of the presence of cardiac glycoside (toxins), the crude protein content of the defatted seed ranges from 42.79 – 47.50/100 g of the seed cake while crude lipid ranges from 4.40 to 4.80/100 g.

All parts of *Thevetia peruviana* plants contain toxic glycosides, the major one reported in seed being thevetin a bitter principle glycoside with a powerful cardiac action. The presence of theveridoside, digitoxigenin, cerberin, peruvoside and theveside has been established in the plant by different workers. The toxicity of the glycoside is reflected in the accidental poisonings that occur among children that feed on the seed of the plants. Some adults have reportedly died after consuming oleander leaves in herbal teas (Shumaik, 1988), about ten fruits may be fatal to an adult while kernel of one fruit may be fatal to children. Generally, small children and livestock are at higher risk. Sign and symptom of poisoning include diarrhoea, headache, vomiting, dizziness, dryness of the throat, burning pain in the mouth, tingling and numbness of the tongue, dilated pupils and loss of muscular power. The pulse first becomes weak which later rapid and irregular. Death occurs from peripheral circulatory failure. Titanic convulsions are sometimes observed, when 8 to 10 seeds which, proves fatal to an adult, causing death within 24 hours.

The active principles are the three glycosides, namely: thevetin, thevotoxin and cereberin. Thevetin and thevotoxin are isolated from of the seeds. Thevetin and cerberin reside in the milky juice which exudes from all parts of the plant. Thevetin is a powerful cardiac poison. Thevotoxin is less toxic and resembles the glycosides of digitalis in action. Cerberin has strychnine-like action. The root and seeds of yellow oleander are used for suicide by women in certain parts of India, on account of dowry problems or matrimonial mishaps. They are also used for abortion. Cattle poisoning occurs when the seeds are crushed, mixed with fodder, and fed to the animal.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant material

The seed of *Thevetia peruviana* plant was obtained from the different places in and around Allahabad and it was scientifically identified by the Department of Horticulture, SHIATS, Allahabad. Seeds are kept in shade for drying.

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Animals

Wister albino rat of male sex, weighing 250 to 300 g was used for the study. The rats were procured and kept in animal house of United Institute of Pharmacy, Allahabad. They were allowed free access to drinking water, standard diet and kept in standard temperature (20-25°C).

Ethical clearance

Ethical permission for conducting experiment on Albino rat was obtained from Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (IAEC), United Institute of Pharmacy, UCER, A-31/1, UPSIDC, Industrial Area, Naini, Allahabad-211010, Uttar Pradesh. All procedures were reviewed and approved by IAEC-UIP. Followed CPCSEA requirements under Reg. No.1451/PO/a/11 dt.02.08.2011.

Seed extract preparation

All collected seed samples of different regions of Allahabad are mixed thoroughly and 400 grams of *Thevetia peruviana* seed was taken, cleaned crushed and grinded for 3-4 times and sieved using sieves of appropriate mesh size. The powdered seed was then extracted using 50% ethanol by Soxhlet extractor. The percentage yield was 11.5% w/w.

Antidote preparation

Two different types of mechanical antidote were prepared by mixing following ingredients.

- a. Antidote number 3- Charcoal 50%+Rose petal powder 50%
- b. Antidote number 4- Charcoal 50%+Turmeric powder 50%

Experimental Design

Total 16 rats were taken for the experimental purpose which was divided into four groups. The group (I) was treated as control, group (II) rats were treated with seed extract (200mg/kg) whereas group (III & IV) were treated with the antidote number 3 and 4 respectively. The extract and antidotes were administered to the rats intragastrically using BMI feeding tubes.

Sampling

The rats were not allowed to feed for 12 hours before treatment. 12 hours after treatment with seed extract and antidotes, blood was collected in clean and dry centrifuge tubes. The blood was then allowed to clot and serum harvested. The serum was used to assay the following parameters: aspartate transaminase (AST), alanine transaminase (ALT), bilirubin, total protein, urea and creatinine.

Examination

The Serum alanine amino transferase (ALT) and serum aspartate amino transferase (AST) were examined colorimetrically by using the method of Reitman and Frankel (1957). The serum creatinine was examined using the method of Heinegard and Tiderstrom (1973). Estimation of urea was carried out using the Diacetyl monoxime method. Biuret method was used for estimation of serum protein. Serum Bilirubin was estimated using the method of Jendrassik and Grof (1938). All the data was expressed as Mean \pm S.D. The differences between control and treatment groups were tested for significance using one-way ANOVA.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of administration of ethanolic extract of seeds of *Thevetia peruviana* along with antidote 3rd and antidote 4th on liver and kidney function of rats are presented in table 1. Biochemical indices of liver function (AST and ALT) were increased significantly by extract on single dose administration of *Thevetia peruviana* seed extract to experimental group 2nd. The experimental group 4th showed lowered values of ALT and AST more closer to the values of control group when antidote 4th was given along with the seed extract. Slightly higher values of ALT and AST were also observed in the experimental group 3rd which was given seed extract and antidote 3rd as compared to values of experimental group 4th. The bilirubins are not affected much in case of experimental group 2nd when given with single dose of seed extract 200mg/kg body weight. The values of all other experimental groups remained closer to the values of control group. Administration of 200 mg/kg ethanolic extract of the seed of *Thevetia peruviana* to the rats resulted in significant increase in the creatinine levels in case of experimental group 2nd as compared with control group (36.81 \pm 0.70). The creatinine level showed similar values in case of experimental group 4th (38.66 \pm 0.59) when compared to creatinine level of experimental group 3rd. This was slightly higher than the experimental group 4th and showing better result with antidote 4th. The other biochemical indices of kidney function like urea also showed increased values (Fig.1) in case of experimental group 2nd (17.83 \pm 0.31) when administered with 200mg/kg of body weight. The values of experimental groups 4th (12.57 \pm 0.36) remained closer to the values of control group (11.53 \pm 0.41). The haematological parameter like serum protein in experimental rats when administered with 200mg/kg body weight of seed extract in experimental group 2nd showed higher values (86.41 \pm 0.38) when compared to control group. The serum protein values of experimental group 4th showed closer

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values (73.19 ± 0.47) as compared to the control group having 72.70 ± 0.86 g/l. The serum protein values of experimental group 3rd remains higher (78.75 ± 0.24) as compared to the values of experimental group 4th showing better performance of antidote 4th than that of antidote 3rd.

Figure 1: Result of screening of antidote for *Thevetia peruviana* (Yellow Oleander) on the basis of different biochemical parameters

Table 1: Screening of antidote for *Thevetia peruviana* (Yellow Oleander) on the basis of different biochemical parameters

Parameters	Control Group	Experimental Group 2 nd Seed Extract 200 mg/kg	Experimental Group 3 rd (Seed Extract 200 mg/kg and Antidote 3 rd (200 mg/kg))	Experimental Group 4 th (Seed Extract 200 mg/kg and Antidote 4 th 200 mg/kg)
ALT (u/L)	40.63 ± 0.42	49.63 ± 0.54	46.55 ± 0.62	41.58 ± 1.10
AST (u/L)	41.55 ± 0.62	51.43 ± 0.39	43.95 ± 0.63	41.94 ± 0.34
Serum Creatinine (mMol/L)	36.81 ± 0.70	44.28 ± 0.71	43.37 ± 0.81	38.66 ± 0.59
Serum Bilirubin (µmol/L)	1.39 ± 0.35	2.52 ± 0.31	1.53 ± 0.09	1.49 ± 0.04
Serum Urea (mMol/L)	11.53 ± 0.41	17.83 ± 0.31	13.93 ± 0.40	12.57 ± 0.36
Serum Protein (g/L)	72.70 ± 0.86	86.41 ± 0.38	78.75 ± 0.24	73.19 ± 0.47

Values are presented as Mean ± SD.

The present study showed significant increase in AST and ALT values and slight increase in bilirubin values indicate the toxic effect of seed extract of *Thevetia peruviana* on liver function of rats showing hepatotoxic activity of the extract. Similar findings have been reported by Langford and Boor (1999) in humans intoxicated with oleander fruits. Experimental result showed normal values when antidote 4th was administered along with the seed extract. Urea increased in experimental group was no significant however increased in the cretanine level was quite significant was one of the most important indicator of kidney function .Our result showed possible renal mal functions as suggested by Shawn and Pearn (1979) in human by oleander poisoning. This returned to its normal function with the use of antidote 4th in experimental group 4 again showing better result for antidote no.4 rather than experimental group 3rd which was given antidote 3rd. Serum protein concentration is increased in seed extract treated group. Normal range was observed with the application of antidote 4th. Statistical analysis of parameters indicates significant effect of antidote 4th on toxicity of seed extract in albino rats. This significant effect was not observed in case of antidote 3rd.

CONCLUSION

Study have been conducted to see the effect of prepreaed antidote on toxicity of *Thevetia peruviana* seed extrat in Albino rat by screening the different biochemical parameters such as AST ,ALT, Urea, Protein, Cretinine and Bilirubin using blood serum. Observation reveled that experimental group 4th showed lowered values of ALT and AST more closer to the values of control group when antidote 4th was given along with the seed extract which was

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not observed in case of experimental group 3rd who was administered with antidote number 3. The other biochemical indices of kidney function like urea, creatinine and serum protein were also found more closure to control group. It was finally concluded that antidote number 4 was showing better result in comparison to antidote number 3. Finally it was concluded that antidote number 4 can be effectively used for *Thevetia peruviana* poisoning to render the onset of toxic effect.

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